

Supplemental Table S1. Back-transformed model-predicted means, SE, and 95% CI for all outcomes scored, along with model outputs

Raw and back-transformed model predicted means (obtained using type="response" in emmeans in R) and CI:

Behavior	Baseline d 2		Restriction d 2		Return d 1		Return d 2	
	Means (SE)	95% CI	Means (SE)	95% CI	Means (SE)	95% CI	Means (SE)	95% CI
Eating (raw; proportion)	0.347 (0.012)	[0.324,0.369]	0.160 (0.004)	[0.152,0.168]	0.442 (0.009)	[0.424,0.460]	0.358 (0.011)	[0.335,0.382]
Eating (model-predicted; proportion)	0.346 (0.009)	[0.328,0.364]	0.160 (0.007)	[0.148,0.174]	0.442 (0.010)	[0.423,0.461]	0.358 (0.009)	[0.340,0.376]
Intersucking (raw; time, s/12 h)	7 (2)	[3,10]	27 (7)	[12,42]	7 (3)	[2,12]	10 (5)	[0,19]
Intersucking (raw; number of bouts, #/12 h)	1.4 (0.3)	[0.6,2.1]	1.1 (0.3)	[0.4,1.8]	1.3 (0.3)	[0.6,2.1]	1.4 (0.5)	[0.3,2.4]
Intersucking (raw; bout length, s/bout)	3 (1)	[1,5]	23 (5)	[11,34]	2 (1)	[1,3]	3 (1)	[1,5]

Generalized linear mixed model (beta distribution) results:

Behavior	Anova (type III SS)		
	DF*	chisq	P-value
Eating	3,78	678.520	<0.001
Baseline d 2 vs. Restriction d 2	-	-	<0.001
Baseline d 2 vs. Return d 1	-	-	<0.001
Baseline d 2 vs. Return d 2	-	-	0.713
Restriction d 2 vs. Return d 1	-	-	<0.001
Restriction d 2 vs. Return d 2	-	-	<0.001
Return d 1 vs. Return d 2	-	-	<0.001

Wilcoxon signed rank test results:

Intersucking	Time (s/12 h)		Number of bouts (#/12 h)		Bout length (s/bout)	
	V	P-value	V	P-value	V	P-value
Day comparison (paired)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Baseline d 2 vs. Restriction d 2	28.5	0.026	58.5	0.379	3	<0.001
Baseline d 2 vs. Return d 1	101	0.825	87	0.965	100.5	0.528
Baseline d 2 vs. Return d 2	115	0.723	107	0.642	101	0.896
Restriction d 2 vs. Return d 1	160.5	0.009	59.5	0.432	174	0.002
Restriction d 2 vs. Return d 2	174	0.011	81.5	0.878	187	0.002
Return d 1 vs. Return d 2	56.5	0.569	67.5	0.670	49	0.339

*DF obtained from the Anova type III SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>) In reviewing the model summary to confirm conservative analysis outside of DF output, "PenID" is correctly identified as the group (random effect; 21 pairs of heifers)

Supplemental Figure S1. Total mixed ration (TMR; alfalfa, almond hulls, cottonseed, corn, barley, beet pulp) fed to year-old heifers.